

CODE 326**THE STRENGTHENING OF FLOOR AND ROOF MASONRY RING BEAMS
WITH FIBRE-BASED COMPOSITE MATERIALS: EXPERIMENTAL TESTS****Ingrid Boem¹; Natalino Gattesco²; Emanuele Rizzi³, Matija Gams⁴**

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ABSTRACT

The paper collects the results of some experimental tests carried out to assess the behaviour floor and roof masonry ring beams strengthened with composite materials. Two different techniques are considered. The former consists in the reconstruction of the masonry of the roof ring beam by embedding Glass Fibre Reinforced Polymer (GFRP) preformed meshes in the bed joints; the latter in wrapping the floor/roof ring beam by means of Carbon Fibre Reinforced Polymer (CFRP) strips bonded on the outer surface of the building. The tests are carried out on full-scale masonry beams samples with a span of about 3.0/3.6 m and two different masonry types are considered: solid brick masonry (250 mm thick) and rubble stone masonry (350 mm thick). The samples are subjected to horizontal cyclic bending. The results, collected in terms of applied load varying the net deflection, evidence the effectiveness of both the proposed measures to provide bending resistance to the masonry ring beams also at high levels of deflection, thus proving effectiveness against the out-of-plane failure of masonry walls but also compatibility with the mechanical characteristics of historic masonry.

KEYWORDS: Masonry; Ring beams; Composites; Fibre Reinforced Polymer (FRP)

1. INTRODUCTION

Traditional masonry buildings hit by earthquakes often experience damage caused by the out-of-plane failure of masonry walls [1]. Floor tie rods or RC ring beams at roof and floor levels can mitigate this occurrence and foster of the global, box-like behaviour of the structure [2]. Modern strengthening solutions for masonry ring-beams, based on the application of fibre-based composites to the masonry surface or embedded in the bed joints, have been recently developed and investigated [3]-[5].

The paper presents the results of full-scale, experimental cyclic tests performed of masonry ring beam elements to investigate of the capabilities of two different strengthening techniques, against out-of-plane horizontal bending. The former technique (Figure 1a) consists in the reconstruction of the roof ring beam by embedding Glass Fibre-Reinforced Polymer (GFRP) preformed meshes in the bed joints; the latter (Figure 1b), in wrapping the floor/roof ring beam by means of Carbon Fibre-Reinforced Polymer (CFRP) strips bonded on the outer surface of the building. Two different masonry types are considered: solid brick masonry (masonry type “1” and rubble stone masonry (type “2”).

Figure 1: The strengthening of masonry beams with composites: (a) GFRP meshes embedded in the bed joints and (b) externally-bonded CFRP strips.

2. GEOMETRY

To evaluate the effectiveness of the two fibre-based strengthening techniques, two different types of sample (“A” and “B”) are conceived. Samples “A” (Figure 2a) are simple straight masonry beams having a 3500 mm length. The beam height is 465 mm for the solid-brick masonry sample A1 (6 bed joints are included) and 660 mm for rubble stone masonry sample A2 (4 bed joints); a GFRP mesh is embedded in each bed joint. Samples “B” (Figure 2b) have a C-shape composed of a 3650 mm long web and 1035 mm long wings; the height is 1000 mm and the CFRP strip is bonded to the outer surface, at the mid height, rounding the corners with a bend radius of 20 mm. In fact, in case of eccentric bonded strip, the continuity of the reinforcement along the building’s perimeter is essential to provide the bending resistance when the loading deflected the beam internally. This justifies the choice of a C-shape sample, instead of a simple straight beam, so to account for the interaction with orthogonal walls. The solid-brick masonry sample is named B1, the rubble stone one B2.

Figure 2: Main geometric characteristics of (a) A1-A2 and (b) B1-B2 samples.

3. MATERIALS

The samples are made of solid clay brick masonry, 250 mm thick (herein called masonry type “1”), and rubble stone masonry, 350 mm thick (herein called masonry type “2”). For both masonry types, a weak natural lime mortar is used (hydraulic lime-to-sand ratio of 1:7 by mass; average flexural and compressive strength 0.21 MPa and 1.90 MPa). The solid clay bricks (120x55x250 mm³, nominal compressive strength of 18 MPa) are arranged in single leaf in accordance to the “English bond” pattern. Differently, the sandstone units (mean compressive strength 150-170 MPa) are arranged in a two-leaf masonry configuration.

The GFRP mesh has a regular square grid (pitch 66 mm²), composed of twisted fibre wires in the warp direction weaved on parallel fibres wires in the weft direction (dry fibre cross section in a wire 3.8 mm²). The tensile strength and Young modulus of the twisted wires (1345 MPa and 72816 MPa, respectively) are slightly lower than those of the parallel fibre wires (1561 MPa and 76711 MPa). In the ring beam samples, the meshes are disposed with the twisted wires parallel to the beam length.

The unidirectional CFRP strip (200 mm wide, with a dry fibre cross section 66.6 mm², technical sheet values: tensile strength 4700 MPa, Young modulus 390 GPa, tensile ultimate strain 1.2% [6]) is applied on the masonry after levelling the surface with thixotropic cementitious grout and spreading a first layer of epoxy resin (technical sheet values: tensile/compressive strength 60 MPa, Young modulus 3 GPa, tensile ultimate strain 2.9% [7-8]). Then, the strip is positioned and another epoxy resin layer was applied. Epoxy-impregnated CFRP coupons provided mean experimental values of tensile strength and Young modulus equal to 1314.3 MPa and 353 GPa.

4. METHODS

The test setup for “A” samples (Figure 3a) is composed of two supports, at the beam lateral extremities, providing contrast against out-of-plane horizontal translation, but allowing rotations. The net span between the supports is 3000 mm. To alternately pulling (negative loading) and pushing (positive loading) the sample, the piston of a double-effect hydraulic actuator, located in correspondence of the mid span, is moved horizontally by a hand pump. Two load cells and three pairs of displacement transducers monitor the push/pull forces (F) and the absolute horizontal out-of-plane displacements at mid span and both supports. The sample net deflection, δ_m , was evaluated by subtracting the mean supports displacements to the mid-span one.

The loading system for testing “B” samples (Figure 3b) is identical to the previous, with the double-effect hydraulic actuator applying the horizontal cyclic force at the mid span. In addition, horizontal roller constrains (composed of pairs of tie rods provided with knuckle joints) are created at the ends of sample wings, so that rotations about the vertical axis are prevented but horizontal translation allowed. The masonry wings are in simple contact with the roller constraint system; differently, the CFRP strip is connected by means of tightened steel plates, to reproduce the continuity of the bonded strip around the building’s perimeter in actual strengthening interventions. Two pressure transducers and two pairs of displacement transducers monitor the push/pull forces (F) and the horizontal out-of-plane displacements at mid span (at both inner and outer side).

Both “A” and “B” samples lie on series of independent trolleys allowing the free translation and deformation of the sample. The amplitude of the mid-span deflection, δ_m , is cyclically increased during the tests; then, once the sample collapses in pushing, the test is continued by pulling monotonically.

Figure 3: Test setup for (a) “A” and (b) “B” samples.

5. RESULTS

The tests results of the “A” samples are schematized in Figure 4 in terms of load-deflection (F - δ_m) capacity curves. It is observed that the envelope curves progress almost tri-linearly (elastic - hardening - plastic phases). The damage pattern evolution consists of a series of sub-vertical cracks that form progressively from the mid-span and gradually spread over a wider beam portion, as the deflection increases. This is possible for the presence of the GFRP mesh embedded in the mortar joints, that carries the tensile stresses in the cracked masonry. The cracks develop throughout the whole sample height, following the mortar joints. The inversion of the bending action determines the alternative opening and closing of the cracks at the front and back sides; the crack width increases with the deflection amplitude. The peak load is reached immediately before the failure of the GFRP longitudinal wires in the central portion of the beam, close to the tensed side, then the load rapidly drop down.

Figure 4: Load-deflection capacity curves of (a) A1 and (b) A2 samples.

In sample “A1” (Figure 4a), made of solid brick masonry, the first cracking occurs at the front side for $F = +2.6$ kN ($\delta_m = +2.3$ mm), and at the back side for $F = -3.1$ kN ($\delta_m = -2.7$ mm). The cracks formation is almost completed at $\delta_m = \pm 30$ mm; then, a consistent widening of the central cracks is observed. Also, the progressive formation of a continuous horizontal discontinuity at the height of the upper joint determines the gradual separation of the last brick row from the lower part of the sample. The sample attained to $F = -12.4$ kN ($\delta_m = -105.1$ mm) when some longitudinal GFRP wires at the rear face failed in tension, at the mid-span (Figure 5). At the opposite loading direction, the load attains $F = +9.0$ kN (δ_m

= +101.9 mm).

In sample “A2” (Figure 4b), made of rubble stone masonry, the first cracks open at the rear face for $F = -2.3$ kN ($\delta_m = -1$ mm) and at the front face for $F = +5.2$ kN ($\delta_m = +0.8$ mm). From $\delta_m = \pm 16$ mm, no other sub-vertical main cracks appear; instead, a gradual and significant widening of the central cracks emerges. The failure of the GFRP wires, leading to the sample collapse, occurs for $F = -18.0$ kN ($\delta_m = -68.8$ mm) and $F = +18.6$ kN ($\delta_m = +69.0$ mm) - Figure 6.

Figure 5: Sample A1 at collapse (when pushing): (a) global view and (b) detail at mid-span.

Figure 6: Sample A2 at collapse (when pulling): (a) global view and (b) detail at mid-span.

The load-deflection ($F-\delta_m$) graphs of the “B” samples are plotted in Figure 7. The trend of the envelope curves is asymmetric, due to the eccentric reinforcement that intervenes in different ways, depending on the loading direction. For the positive direction (when pushing from the inner to the outer side) the trend is approximately elastic since the masonry is uncracked. Then, as a vertical crack opens in the masonry at the mid-span, on the outer side, the stiffness significantly reduces and a plastic trend with hardening emerges. A few additional vertical cracks appear, in the vicinity of the former; then the CFRP strip fractures at the mid span and the load abruptly drops down. For the negative direction, the trend is elastic till cracking at the mid-span, on the inner side; this induces at first sudden load decrease, which however tends gradually to be recovered. The load furtherly increase till the attainment of the masonry cracking in proximity of the corners, at the outer side, and, subsequently, till the tensile failure of the CFRP Fibres at those cracked sections.

Figure 7: Load-deflection capacity curves of (a) B1 and (b) B2 samples.

In sample B1, the first cracks occur for $F = +10.4$ kN ($\delta_m = +1.7$ mm) and $F = -14.8$ kN ($\delta_m = -4.5$ mm); the failure of the fibres is reached at the mid span for $F = +22.9$ kN ($\delta_m = +26.0$ mm) - Figure 8a, and at the corners for $F = -22.2$ kN ($\delta_m = -52.8$ mm) - Figure 8b. Some CFRP debonding was noted around those sections, just before the fibres rupture.

The first cracking in the rubble stone sample, B2, occurs at $F = +9.6$ kN ($\delta_m = +1.2$ mm) and at $F = -14.0$ kN ($\delta_m = -1.2$ mm). The fibres failure activates at the mid span for $F = +29.6$ kN ($\delta_m = +19.5$ mm) - Figure 9a. Loading in the negative direction, an anticipated fracturing affects some impregnated fibres at the right clamp ($F = -20.3$ kN, $\delta_m = -24.1$ mm), likely due to a local stress concentration induced by an excessive clamping. Then, the cracking of the masonry close to the left corner and the tensile failure of the CFRP strip in correspondence of the fold at left corner, also accompanied by local debonding, is attained for $F = -17.3$ kN ($\delta_m = -44.4$ mm) - Figure 9b.

Figure 8: Fibres failure in sample B (a) at the mid span, in pushing, and (b) at the corners, in pulling.

Figure 9: Fibres failure in sample B (a) at the mid span, in pushing, and (b) at the corners, in pulling.

In Figure 10 the results of the four tests are resumed in terms of load and deflection associated to first cracking and peak. The ratio between peak and first cracking condition can roughly provide an estimation of the reinforcement benefits in respect to the unstrengthened configuration. It is observed that the ratio F_{peak}/F_{crack} ranges between 3.5 and 7.8 in A samples, and 1.5 and 3.1 in B samples. The ratio $\delta_{m,peak}/\delta_{m,crack}$ varies in the ranges 39-86 and 12-37, respectively.

Figure 10: Experimental comparisons in terms of (a) load and (b) deflection at the occurrence of first crack and peak load.

6. CONCLUSIONS

GFRP meshes embedded in the bed joints and externally bonded CFRM strips have been investigated as strengthening solutions for masonry ring beams aimed at contrasting out-of-plane mechanisms in masonry buildings. Quasi-static cyclic tests have been performed on solid brick and rubble stone strengthened masonry ring beams, to investigate on bending resistance, deflection capacities and failure mode. In both cases, the fibres intervene in carrying the tensile stresses originated by bending, allowing high deformation and increasing the resistance.

The beams with the GFRP meshes in the bed joints perform symmetrically as the load reversed: the longitudinal wires activated alternatively at the opposite masonry sides. Due to the diffuse reinforcement, several sub-vertical cracks formed in the masonry, in a wide area of the sample, till achieving the fibres failure at the mid span. The fully embedment of the mesh within the mortar is fundamental to avoid masonry rows separation at high deflections.

The external CFRM strip, even though eccentric, is effective regardless the load direction: when deflecting outside, the fibres activate at the mid-span; when inside, at the corners. The continuity of the reinforcement throughout orthogonal walls is thus essential. Just a few, wide sub-vertical cracks (at mid span and at corners) form in the masonry. The ultimate deflection was appreciably lower in the former case. An adequate bend radius of the strip is necessary to prevent premature fracture at the corners.

The next steps of the research include the development of simple analytical formulations for the prediction of the bending capacity and the calibration of predictive numerical models for reinforced masonry ring beams, to realistically simulate the effect of the investigated reinforcements on entire vertical walls subjected to out-of-plane load.

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